

D 2.4 – Simulation results report

EM-TECH - Innovative e-motor technologies covering e-axles and e-corners vehicle architectures for high-efficient and sustainable e-mobility

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long Version
ABS	Anti-lock braking system
AFM	Axial flux motor
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AWD	All-wheel-drive
DRL	Deep reinforcement learning
E-Gear	Electric gear

EM	Electric motor
EV	Electric vehicle
FL	Front left
e-axle	Electric-axle
e-corner	Electric corner
FWD	Front-wheel-drive
HB	Hydraulic brake
HGV	Heavy goods vehicles
HIL	Hardware-in-the-loop
IWM	In-wheel motor
KPIs	Key performance indicators
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LUT	Look-up table
MF	Magic formula
NMPC	Nonlinear model predictive controller
NN	Neural network
OEM	Original equipment manufacturer
PnG	Pulse and glide
PWM	Pulse-width modulation
RL	Rear left
RMSE	Root-mean-square error
RWD	Rear-wheel-drive
TC	Traction control
WLTP	Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicles Test Procedure
WP	Work package
XIL	X-in-the-loop

Partners List

Abbreviation	Long Version
AVL	AVL LIST GMBH

TUIL	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET ILMENAU
POLITO	POLITECNICO DI TORINO
ELA	ELAPHE POGONSKE TEHNOLOGIJE DOO
I&M	IDEAS & MOTION SRL
URBANGOLD	URBANGOLD GMBH
AIG	ARMENGAUD INNOVATE GMBH
USR	UNIVERSITY OF SURREY
UBATH	UNIVERSITY OF BATH
TRX	TRAXIAL BV

Table of Contents

1	Publishable Executive Summary	7
1.1	Overview of project.....	7
1.2	Deliverable Objective and Results.....	7
2	Introduction	7
3	Overview of the vehicle simulation toolchain and simulation blocks	11
3.1	Vehicle simulation toolchain	11
3.2	Component models and low-level control functions.....	11
3.3	High-level control functions	14
3.3.1	Anti-lock brake system.....	14
3.3.2	E-gear shifting strategy	14
3.3.3	Use of onboard motors for Eco-driving	15
3.3.4	Brake blending	17
4	Simulation results for IWMs	19
4.1	Simulation of IWM phase current for E-gear thermal validation	19
4.2	Simulation of virtual motor temperature sensor	21
4.3	Energy consumption assessment and improvement for IWM	25
4.4	Brake blending strategy for energy recycling	27
4.5	Vehicle dynamics improvements for IWM applications using ABS.....	32
4.5.1	Simulation results for hard braking manoeuvre with IWM	33
5	Simulation results for onboard motors	38
5.1	Simulation of modular AFMs for a wide range of vehicle applications	38
5.2	Energy consumption assessment and improvement for onboard motor	39
5.3	Vehicle dynamics improvements for onboard applications using ABS.....	40
5.3.1	Simulation results for hard braking manoeuvre with onboard AFM	42
6	Use of the in-wheel and onboard motor solutions for AI-based traction control applications.....	45
7	Conclusion.....	48
7.1	Deviations, Impact and Recovery Actions.....	48

List of Figures

FIGURE 3.1 VSM AND SIMULINK CO-SIMULATION PLATFORM.	11
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D 2.4 – Simulation results report

FIGURE 3.2 SURROGATE MODEL OF TRACTION MOTOR.	12
FIGURE 3.3 SURROGATE MODEL OF IWM WITH E-GEAR FEATURE.	12
FIGURE 3.4 SURROGATE MODEL OF E-GEAR SYSTEM.	13
FIGURE 3.5 CONTROL LOGIC OF E-GEAR TRANSITION.....	13
FIGURE 3.6 INTERACTIONS BETWEEN GEARBOX AND OTHER VEHICLE COMPONENTS.	13
FIGURE 3.7 BLOCK DIAGRAM OF THE NMPC	14
FIGURE 3.8 DIFFERENT RULE-BASED GEAR-SHIFTING STRATEGIES FOR NORMALIZED EFFICIENCY MAP	15
FIGURE 3.9 NORMALIZED POWER LOSS DATA AT DIFFERENT SPEEDS.....	16
FIGURE 3.10 DIFFERENT LEVELS OF NON-CONVEXITY IN THE NORMALIZED POWER LOSS MAP NEAR THE ZERO-TORQUE RANGE. (A) LEVEL 1 (b) LEVEL 2 (c) LEVEL 3	17
FIGURE 3.11 PNG BLOCK DIAGRAM FOR MAINTAINING DESIRED SPEED	17
FIGURE 3.12 PROPOSED BRAKE BLENDING CONTROLLER ARCHITECTURE	18
FIGURE 4.1 IWM PHASE CURRENT PROFILES FOR THE WLTP DRIVING CYCLE.....	20
FIGURE 4.2 MOTOR RESPONSES OF ELA'S BASELINE IWM FOR WLTP DRIVING CYCLE: COOLANT 60°C, AMBIENT 20°C.....	22
FIGURE 4.3 MOTOR RESPONSES OF ELA'S BASELINE IWM FOR WLTP DRIVING CYCLE: COOLANT 70°C, AMBIENT 40°C.....	22
FIGURE 4.4 MOTOR RESPONSES OF ELA'S BASELINE IWM FOR WLTP DRIVING CYCLE: COOLANT 50°C, AMBIENT 10°C.....	23
FIGURE 4.5 MOTOR RESPONSES OF ELA'S BASELINE IWM FOR ARTEMIS DRIVING CYCLE: COOLANT 70°C, AMBIENT 40°C.....	23
FIGURE 4.6 MOTOR RESPONSES OF ELA'S BASELINE IWM FOR ARTEMIS DRIVING CYCLE: COOLANT 60°C, AMBIENT 20°C.....	24
FIGURE 4.7 MOTOR RESPONSES OF ELA'S BASELINE IWM FOR ARTEMIS DRIVING CYCLE: COOLANT 50°C, AMBIENT 10°C.....	24
FIGURE 4.8 SPEED TRACKING PERFORMANCE FOR THE WLTP DRIVING CYCLE BASED ON CASE 1 RULE-BASED GEAR-SHIFTING	27
FIGURE 4.9 POSSIBLE REGENERATION POWER FOR THE MOTOR, NORMALIZED TO 100 UNITS FOR THE MAXIMUM POWER.....	28
FIGURE 4.10 OPTIMIZED REGENERATION TORQUE AND CORRESPONDING POWER AVAILABLE FOR BRAKING	29
FIGURE 4.11 VELOCITY TRACKING PERFORMANCE OF BRAKE BLENDING CONTROLLERS. CLOSE SPEED VALUES MEAN THAT ALL TESTED CONTROLLERS WERE UNDER EQUAL TEST CONDITIONS.....	30
FIGURE 4.12 COMPARISON OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF DIFFERENT CONFIGURATIONS DURING A WLTP CYCLE.....	30
FIGURE 4.13 SIMULATED TORQUE DEMANDED FROM IWM DURING BRAKING	31
FIGURE 4.14 BRAKE MANOEUVRE RESULTS WITH E-GEAR SWITCHING, REGULATED TORQUE FROM THE (A) IWM (B) HB	33
FIGURE 4.15 BRAKE MANOEUVRE RESULTS FOR PURELY HYDRAULIC BRAKING (A) WHEEL SLIP RATIO (B) VEHICLE SPEED AND WHEEL SPEED (C) REGULATE AND UNREGULATED TORQUE FROM HB	35
FIGURE 4.16 BRAKE MANOEUVRE RESULTS FOR BRAKE BLENDING IN SERIES CONFIGURATION (A) WHEEL SLIP RATIO (B) VEHICLE SPEED AND WHEEL SPEED (C) REGULATED AND UNREGULATED TORQUE FROM (c) HB (d) IWMS	36
FIGURE 4.17 BRAKE MANOEUVRE RESULTS FOR BRAKE BLENDING IN PARALLEL CONFIGURATION (A) WHEEL SLIP RATIO (B) VEHICLE SPEED AND WHEEL SPEED (C) REGULATED AND UNREGULATED TORQUE FROM (c) HB (d) IWMS	37
FIGURE 5.1 SPEED TRACKING PERFORMANCE FOR A 50 KM/H CONSTANT SPEED MANOEUVRE, COMPARING RESULTS WITH (B) AND WITHOUT (A) THE APPLICATION OF PULSE-AND-GLIDE (PNG).	40
FIGURE 5.2 TORSIONAL DYNAMICS OF THE ONBOARD SOLUTION	41
FIGURE 5.3 TORQUE RESPONSE OF THE MOTOR (A) WITH (B) WITHOUT TORSIONAL DYNAMICS	42
FIGURE 5.4 BRAKE MANOEUVRE RESULTS FOR PURELY HYDRAULIC BRAKING (A) WHEEL SLIP RATIO (B) VEHICLE SPEED AND WHEEL SPEED (C) REGULATE AND UNREGULATED TORQUE FROM HB	43
FIGURE 5.5 BRAKE MANOEUVRE RESULTS FOR BRAKE BLENDING (A) WHEEL SLIP RATIO (B) VEHICLE SPEED AND WHEEL SPEED (C) REGULATE AND UNREGULATED TORQUE FROM (c) HB (d) ON-BOARD MOTOR	44
FIGURE 6.1 SIMPLIFIED SCHEMATIC OF THE TRAINING FRAMEWORK OF THE DRL-TC	45
FIGURE 6.2 DRL TRAINING, SEGMENT A: EPISODIC REWARD (BLACK SOLID LINE) AND AVERAGE REWARD (RED SOLID LINE)	46
FIGURE 6.3 SIMULATION RESULTS, WHEEL SLIP AND TORQUE REQUEST IN THE CASE OF IN-WHEEL POWERTRAINS: (A) SEGMENT A AND (B) SEGMENT D.	46

D 2.4 – Simulation results report

FIGURE 6.4 SIMULATION RESULTS, WHEEL SLIP AND TORQUE REQUEST IN THE CASE OF ONBOARD MOTOR POWERTRAIN: (A) SEGMENT A AND (B) SEGMENT D.....	47
FIGURE 6.5 VEHICLE ACCELERATION FOR SEGMENT A (A) ONBOARD AND (B) IN-WHEEL SOLUTION.	47

List of Tables

TABLE 2.1 VEHICLE SEGMENTS WITH DIFFERENT DRIVETRAIN LAYOUT.....	8
TABLE 4.1 ENERGY CONSUMPTION PER DISTANCE (WH/KM) AND PERCENTAGE DIFFERENCE IN ENERGY EFFICIENCY FOR VARIOUS VEHICLE SEGMENTS AND DRIVETRAINS ACROSS DIFFERENT DRIVING SCENARIOS.	25
TABLE 4.2 RESULTS OF CONTROLLER TESTING ON THE WLTP CYCLE, DIVIDED BY SECTIONS WITH DIFFERENT AVERAGES OF VELOCITIES	32
TABLE 4.3 KPI VALUES FOR THE NMPC CONTROLLERS FOR IN-WHEEL CONFIGURATIONS.....	34
TABLE 5.1 WLTP ENERGY LOSS ANALYSIS UNDER DIFFERENT PWM FREQUENCIES	38
TABLE 5.2 ENERGY/DISTANCE IMPROVEMENT (%) FOR A VOLKSWAGEN ID.3 ACROSS DIFFERENT DRIVETRAIN CONFIGURATIONS AND DRIVING SCENARIOS, WITH AND WITHOUT THE USE OF PNG STRATEGIES. CRUISE MODE IS THE REFERENCE (REF) HERE.	39
TABLE 5.3 KPI VALUES FOR THE NMPC CONTROLLERS FOR ON-BOARD CONFIGURATIONS.	42

1 Publishable Executive Summary

1.1 Overview of project

The EM-TECH project advances the boundaries of electric machine technology for automotive traction by introducing innovative solutions, including: i) advanced direct and active cooling designs; ii) virtual sensing capabilities for high-fidelity, real-time machine operating condition estimation; iii) improved machine control strategies reducing conservatism, leveraging real-time insights; iv) electric gearing (E-gear) for enhanced operational flexibility and energy efficiency; v) digital twin-based optimization, incorporating Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) considerations from the initial design stages; and vi) the use of recycled permanent magnets and circularity-focused solutions. These innovations enhance radial flux direct-drive in-wheel motors (IWMs) for higher torque density levels, and on-board axial flux motors (AFMs) for superior power density. The project aims to deliver cost-effective, energy-efficient technologies with reduced rare earth dependency and integrated magnet recycling for passenger cars, vans, and scalable commercial vehicles.

1.2 Deliverable Objective and Results

D2.4 is related to T2.4 where comprehensive simulation activities are carried out to assess the vehicle performance improvement resulting from the EM-TECH motor solutions: 1) the modular motor solution is assessed through a wide range of vehicle applications; 2) the high-efficient motor solution is demonstrated from WLTP drive cycle simulation, supported by advanced pulse and glide (PnG) control and brake blending strategy for further energy consumption reduction and also supported by virtual motor temperature sensor; 3) the E-gear IWM solution is evaluated by optimal gear shifting strategies; 4) the rapid-response motor solution is leveraged by an advanced anti-brake system (ABS) and traction control (TC) development. It is demonstrated that the simulation toolchain developed in D2.4 has been instrumental in advancing the EM-TECH project. By enabling the integration, evaluation, and continuous refinement of cutting-edge e-axle and e-corner technologies, the toolchain has provided valuable insights into vehicle-level performance. It effectively assesses the impact of design decisions on energy efficiency, thermal behaviour, and advanced vehicle control strategies, such as pulse-and-glide, ABS, TC, gear-shifting, and virtual sensing techniques, under both WLTP and real-world operation conditions. The toolchain has successfully bridged the gap between component-level development and vehicle-level performance assessment, ensuring alignment with technical requirements and design objectives. Its flexibility in supporting rapid updates and re-parameterisation has been crucial in accommodating advancements from component suppliers, thus promoting strong collaboration among project partners.

2 Introduction

The EM-TECH project aims to push the limit of electric machine technology by developing innovative solutions for high-torque density AFM and direct-drive IWMs for automotive traction, targeting the vehicle segments outline in Table 2.1 with different real-world operating conditions. This goal is supported by the innovative cooling designs, virtual sensing for temperature estimation, and advance high- and low-level controllers to optimise system efficiency and reliability. Work package 2 (WP2) defines the scope and technical requirements of the EM-TECH motor and drives, addressing LCA and LCC aspects detailed

in D2.1 and D2.2, respectively. Using a simulation toolchain developed in D2.3 and validated with experimental data, the performance of the EM-TECH electric-corner (e-corner) module and electric-axes (e-axes) solutions has been evaluated through comprehensive simulation. The outcomes of WP2 will support the R&D activities in WP3-5 and lay the foundation for the test plans and activities in WP6. The work package consists of four tasks and led by USR.

D2.4 focuses on assessing the vehicle-level impact of EM-TECH components under various operation conditions, such as WLTP driving cycle and real-world cycles for different vehicle configurations. This evaluation leverages a comprehensive simulation toolchain for e-axle and e-corner solutions to assess system performance in key areas, including motor temperature estimation, vehicle energy consumption and regeneration, and vehicle stability control.

The simulation-based validation detailed in D2.3 relies on the surrogate models provided by the EM-TECH’s component and system suppliers. These surrogate models are derived either from experimental validated data of their respective components or from high-fidelity simulation data of their validated models. Section 3 provides an overview of the simulation toolchain and simulation blocks used in AVL’s high-fidelity vehicle simulator. The developed simulation toolchain is introduced in section 3.1, which incorporates a high-fidelity vehicle simulator that includes surrogate models of the E-gear IWMs for e-corner and the onboard AFM for e-axes solutions. High- and low-level controllers detailed in D5.1 have enabled the analysis of the performance at the vehicle level using the EM-TECH components and will be implemented in Simulink for co-simulation with the vehicle dynamic simulation Software (AVL VSM™). Section 3 also includes a general description of high-level controllers of PnG, ABS, E-gear shifting, brake blending, and TC incorporating AI technology. These controllers are used to evaluate the performance of the e-axle and e-corner components across various vehicle segments (A to D, M, small van, and HGV) with different drivetrain layouts, as outlined in Table 2.1, highlighted by shaded cells.

Table 2.1 Vehicle segments with different drivetrain layout

Seg.		A	B	C	D	M	Small Van	Heavy goods vehicles (HGVs)
Vehicle model		Fiat 500e	Peugeot e-208	VW ID.3 Style	BMW 320i Sport Saloon 2L Petrol	Audi Q4 Sport 50 e-tron Quattro	Fiat E-DOBLÒ 2-seat van	Mercedes-Benz eActros 300 4x2
IWMs	2, Front	✓	✓			✓	✓	
	2, Rear			✓	✓	✓		
	2, Front & 2, Rear					✓		
AFMs	1, Front	✓	✓	✓		✓		
	1, Rear			✓	✓			
	1, Front & 1, Rear			✓		✓		

Sections 4, 5, and 6 sequentially present investigations into IWMs and onboard AFMs across different vehicle segments. Section 4 examines the temperature estimation, vehicle energy consumption and recycling, brake strategy of E-gear IWMs. The simulation of the phase current profile of E-gear IWMs (section 4.1) and motor temperature estimation using virtual sensors (section 4.2), developed by POLITO,

are performed in Segment M under WLTP driving scenarios to analyse the motor thermal performance and optimise the cooling design of the E-gear system by UBATH. Since IWMs present cooling challenges compared to onboard AFMs, innovative motor cooling designs and virtual sensor-based temperature estimation ensure safe operation, particularly when using recycled magnets. Section 4.3 analyses energy consumption using E-gear switching strategy for vehicle segments (A to D, M, and small vans) under WLTP and constant-speed scenarios. These scenarios compare the performance of E-gear IWMs with the baseline IWM from ELA across series, parallel, and optimised configurations within different driving cycle to assess the efficiency of the E-gear system. An optimised brake blending strategy demonstrates significant benefits in maximising energy recovery during braking actions for a vehicle in segment M are analysed under WLTP driving scenarios is presented in section 4.4. Due to the faster dynamic response of IWMs, they can be effectively integrated into ABS, enhancing vehicle stability compared with low-frequency components using hydraulic brakes (HB). The performance of the controller is compared to conventional hydraulic brakes (HB) for ABS. Vehicle segment M is used to evaluate the ABS performance under low-friction conditions, employing nonlinear model predictive control (NMPC) with IWMs (section 4.5) as brake actuators, optimising their integration with the ABS system.

Section 5 extends the energy consumption analysis to onboard AFMs, evaluating motor and inverter losses over the WLTP driving cycle in vehicle segments (A to D and M) and ABS strategy for segments M. This includes an assessment of AFMs from VAI and TRX, where an optimal pulse-width modulation (PWM) frequency is identified to minimise combined losses in the motor and inverter. The onboard AFM, unlike IWMs, utilises a gearbox to maximise traction and brake torque, while IWMs incorporate an E-gear system. For AFMs, the energy consumption assessment focuses on studying PnG strategies, whereas for IWMs, it includes E-gear shifting strategies, temperature profile assessment, and energy regeneration analysis using the IWM as a brake actuator with two different E-gear configurations. Regarding the TRX motor, it is shown that incorporating some non-convexity near the zero-torque range enables the PnG strategy to improve battery power consumption for segment C vehicles across various driving scenarios. The NMPC controller for the on-board AFM is also implemented for the ABS using Vehicle segment M to improve the brake performance due the fast actuation of the electric machine.

Section 6 focuses on the simulation of an AI-based traction controller, integrating E-gear IWMs and onboard AFMs into torque modulation for robust wheel slip control. Due to the faster dynamic response and accurate torque control of IWMs and AFMs, they can be effectively integrated into TC systems, enhancing vehicle stability. Controller performance with EM-TECH components is compared to a passive system for TC. Assessment in vehicle segments A and D with IWM and AFM configurations during acceleration on low-friction conditions is presented in section 6, where surrogate models of the electric motor (EM) are used for TC applications. The EM-TECH surrogate model and TC algorithm enabling this analysis is one of the AI-based TC strategies discussed in D5.2, which has been implemented in the simulation toolchain presented in D2.3.

Utilizing the technical requirements specified in D2.1 and D2.2, it supports the design of model-based components across electrical, electronic, thermal and control levels. Hence, the study presented in Section 6 also provides an example of how the simulation toolchain can support the design and testing of

AI-based vehicle control solutions to improve the longitudinal acceleration and wheel slip tracking on low-friction road.

The simulation results of innovative EM-TECH components offer actionable insights, facilitating the evaluation of system performance and design robustness prior to X-in-the-loop (XIL) and hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) analyses. The simulation toolchain from AVL will guide XIL and HIL experimental work for vehicle performance and efficiency assessment, enabling model-based evaluations of various e-axle and e-corner designs and their subsystems. EM-TECH will enhance the AVL e-drive efficiency tool (in the VSM™) with features such as analytical model validation for new technologies, automated efficiency optimization for design selection, and a data analytics toolchain for improved calibration and comparison of virtual and real-world data, benchmarked against WLTC and real-world cycles.

The simulation tool developed in WP2 offer substantial benefits for technology development involving multiple partners and component suppliers. The adaptability of the simulation toolchain enables rapid updates and re-parameterization of EM-TECH components based on simulation results, facilitating iterative improvements and continuous optimization of EM-TECH components. For instance, the vehicle stability control and motor energy consumption simulations detailed in Sections 4, 5 and 6 of the deliverable were instrumental in assisting the components iteration. It also supports WP5 in the early stages of experimental XIL and HIL system development. The toolchain also allows the introduction of new vehicle parameters for re-evaluation on behalf of prospective OEMs or the provision of easily integrable models for OEMs' evaluation processes, enhancing engagement strategies, which provides a robust model to potential Tier 1 suppliers, OEM vehicle targets, research institutes and universities.

3 Overview of the vehicle simulation toolchain and simulation blocks

3.1 Vehicle simulation toolchain

The EM-TECH project has developed a co-simulation platform, illustrated in Figure 3.1, which integrates AVL VSM 2023 and MATLAB/Simulink 2022b for vehicle simulation. AVL VSM is a commercial vehicle dynamics simulation tool that supports onboard and in-wheel drives for front-, rear-, and all-wheel setups. It also features a Simulink interface, facilitating the development and testing of advanced vehicle control functions. Representative vehicles, listed in document D2.1, are modelled with key parameters such as mass and geometry obtained from publicly available data, while other vehicle details, such as chassis compliance, are based on template information provided in VSM.

Figure 3.1 VSM and Simulink co-simulation platform.

The powertrain components developed in the EM-TECH project, including traction motors, traction inverters, and transmission systems, are integrated into the simulation toolchain as surrogate models which are computationally efficient while maintaining sufficient accuracy. They are implemented in Simulink rather than in VSM, enhancing the flexibility to incorporate innovative features into the simulation environment. The baseline versions of some powertrain components are also included to ensure the simulation toolchain is comprehensive and to facilitate performance comparisons.

The simulation toolchain will be exploited by the project's stakeholders, including OEMs, Tier-1 suppliers, and research institutes and universities. While all stakeholders contribute to the innovation database of components, subsystems and control functions (with proper IP protection), each can focus on their specific interests when using the toolchain to evaluate vehicle performance improvements.

3.2 Component models and low-level control functions

The surrogate model of the traction motors, IWMs by ELA, AFMs by VAI and TRX, is implemented in the simulation toolchain as shown in Figure 3.2. The saturation function enforces the motor's physical limits on high-level motor torque demands. The dynamic torque response (the local motor controller dynamics are considered together) is simplified as a first-order transfer function. The motor losses are either modelled as a whole or categorised into copper loss, core loss, magnet loss, etc, with the temperature's impact on these losses also incorporated into the model. The online temperatures of permanent magnet and stator windings are estimated by a virtual temperature sensor developed by POLITO, which captures the innovative cooling system design.

Figure 3.2 Surrogate model of traction motor.

In EM-TECH, ELA’s IWM features an E-gear system developed by UBATH, where the phase windings consist of two equal sections that can be configured in either series or parallel connections via mechanical switches. This design extends the motor operation range for both torque and speed. As illustrated in Figure 3.3, the IWM with series and parallel windings are individually modelled as Figure 3.2. The E-Gear system selects the outputs of one of these two models as the final outputs of the IWM. The surrogate model of the E-Gear system is shown in Figure 3.4, where a timer is used to represent the typical time duration of the changeover of switch position, accounting for the time from solenoid activation to stable mechanical contact. A safe changeover operation requires zero current in the windings circuit. Therefore, the E-Gear transition logic, shown in Figure 3.5, is designed to manage the process by intervening in the high-level torque demand and waiting until the actual torque stabilises around zero before sending out the gear shifting request to the E-Gear system.

Figure 3.3 Surrogate model of IWM with E-Gear feature.

Figure 3.4 Surrogate model of E-Gear system.

Figure 3.5 Control logic of E-Gear transition.

For e-axis drives, the transmission system model can be simplified to include basic information such as gear ratio and efficiency. However, to enable the investigation of drivetrain dynamics' impact on vehicle longitudinal oscillations, AVL has developed a more detailed model of a 3-speed gearbox optimised for VAI's modular AFM and heavy goods vehicles (HGVs). This gearbox model is integrated into the simulation toolchain as a Simulink S-function. The interactions between the gearbox and other drivetrain components are illustrated in Figure 3.6, where dynamic models of the differential and driveshafts could be considered as well.

Figure 3.6 Interactions between gearbox and other vehicle components.

The main innovation in the traction inverter developed by I&M, which this simulation toolchain can explore is its high efficiency, especially when wide-bandgap power electronic devices are adopted. Therefore, the inverter's surrogate model is represented as a power loss look-up table.

To enable comprehensive simulation activities, additional components such as the high-voltage battery and the Hydraulic Brake (HB) system are also included in the simulation toolchain. The battery model enhances the evaluation of vehicle energy consumption. The HB system supports the development of brake blending strategies and hybrid ABS functionality.

3.3 High-level control functions

High-level controllers are integral to the simulation toolchain, as they coordinate and optimize the integration of EM-TECH components. This enables precise system-level performance evaluations, including motor thermal analysis, energy consumption assessment, and vehicle stability analysis, while supporting the development of advanced control strategies across various vehicle segments and operating scenarios.

3.3.1 Anti-lock brake system

The ABS utilizes a Nonlinear model predictive controller (NMPC) that takes into account actuator dynamics to manipulate braking torque from both the EMs and the HB. The NMPC aims to prevent wheel lock-up, improving the brake distance and vehicle stability during a braking manoeuvre. The control system architecture, illustrated in Figure 3.7 considering brake blending with EM and purely HB. The NMPC conducts the formulation of an optimization problem that allows constraints of the torque limitation to be imposed on both control inputs and system states with a simplified internal predictive model preserving key vehicle dynamics, such as the nonlinear Pacejka MF (Magic Formula) tire model and vertical force estimations at the wheel. Over a finite prediction time horizon, a nonlinear optimal control problem is defined to minimize the cost function involving the slack variables, soft constraints on left and right wheel slip ratio errors, and the control action penalization, where the detailed formulation of the controller is presented in D5.1.

Figure 3.7 Block diagram of the NMPC

3.3.2 E-gear shifting strategy

This section provides an overview of the rule-based gear-shifting strategy designed for IWMs with an E-Gear system detailed in D5.1. The E-Gear motor demonstrates distinct torque-speed operation ranges for series and parallel configurations, with varying efficiencies in the overlapping areas. A gear-shifting strategy can be designed to prioritize operation within the higher-efficiency range in these regions. Two different rule-based gear-shifting strategies, referred to as Case 1 and Case 2 are designed and depicted in

Figure 3.8. To maintain confidentiality, the motor speed and motor torques have been normalized.

Figure 3.8 Different rule-based gear-shifting strategies for normalized efficiency map

The gear-shifting rules in

Figure 3.8 indicate that, in case 1, series configurations are selected when the motor speed is below a certain threshold, and parallel windings are chosen when the speed exceeds this threshold, with the red vertical line marking the transition point.

In case 2 of rule-based gear-shifting, the guideline specifies: on the left side of the red lines, select series configuration; on the right side of the red lines, select parallel configuration.

3.3.3 Use of onboard motors for Eco-driving

Climate change is driving new environmental policies, like the EU and UK's 2035 ban on new petrol and diesel cars, making electric vehicles (EVs) the future of transport. However, limited battery range remains a challenge, highlighting the need to improve energy efficiency. One common solution is the pulse-and-glide (PnG) technique, which involves alternating between periods of acceleration (pulse) and coasting (glide) in a repetitive cycle, while maintaining a target average speed to achieve minimal overall energy consumption [1].

In this study, the Linear Programming (LP) optimization is used to determine the optimal duty cycles associated with the pulsing and glide torques that minimize battery power consumption. The power loss data has been provided by the motor manufacturer TRX. The result of the LP is stored offline in a Look-up Table (LUT) and executed during each PnG period, which is assumed to be 2 seconds. This is referred to as LUT method later on.

While designing the PnG algorithm with TRX motor data, we initially analysed battery power consumption using the original power loss data. However, we found that introducing some non-convexity in the near-zero torque range, as highlighted in [2], could enhance the performance of the PnG algorithm as the data in this region are usually obtained via extrapolation. Accordingly, we implemented three levels of power loss reduction within this torque range.

The power loss data from the TRX motor at various vehicle speeds is shown in Figure 3.9. The vehicle used here is the Volkswagen ID.3, a segment C model. It is important to mention that, for confidentiality reasons, the actual motor torque and power loss data have been normalized.

It is evident that in the near-zero torque range, the curve exhibits a convex shape, which is unfavourable for the PnG strategy.

Figure 3.9 Normalized power loss data at different speeds

Therefore, three distinct levels of power loss reduction near zero torque demand, which contribute to the non-convexity in the power loss map and are beneficial for the PnG methodology, are analysed as shown in Figure 3.10, with Level 3 demonstrating the most significant reduction in power loss near zero torque compared to the other levels.

Figure 3.10 Different levels of non-convexity in the normalized power loss map near the zero-torque range. (a) Level 1 (b) Level 2 (c) Level 3

To implement the PnG controller in the simulation environment, the desired torque from the speed controller, along with the average vehicle speed, is fed into the LUTs generated by LP. These LUTs produce

pulse torque and duty cycle outputs, which are then sent as commands to the corresponding EV powertrains. The choice between PnG and constant torque operation is determined by the LUT output. This LUT-based approach is compared to a purely non-PnG method, referred to as cruise control. While both use a similar speed controller to follow the drive cycle speed, cruise control operates at a frequency of 10 Hz, whereas the LUT functions at 0.5 Hz. The block diagram of PnG controller is shown in Figure 3.11.

Figure 3.11 PnG block diagram for maintaining desired speed

3.3.4 Brake blending

As mentioned in previous deliverables, the experience of integrating simple braking blending strategies in vehicles does not allow to maximize the effect in every operating condition. For example, a fixed blending factor, where the braking torque is shared between actuators, friction torques and motors, or sequential activation of torque mechanisms, where the braking potential of the motor is used first and then the friction torques are connected, can work inefficiently in certain driving modes. For the motors studied, such modes often occur at low speed and high braking torque, or at low braking loads at high speed.

In order to improve the brake blending system and achieve the most efficient return of the vehicle's kinetic energy to the battery, it was proposed to develop a controller based on the optimization function of the regenerated energy. The block diagram of the controller is shown in the Figure 3.12 below:

Figure 3.12 Proposed Brake blending controller architecture

4 Simulation results for IWMs

4.1 Simulation of IWM phase current for E-gear thermal validation

The E-gear system experiences thermal loading due to heat generated by the contact resistance of the mechanical switches that connect the phase windings in either series or parallel configurations. By leveraging the simulation toolchain, phase current profiles of the IWM can be generated for typical driving cycles. These profiles are subsequently used by UBATH to analyse or optimise the thermal design of the E-gear system, which is particularly critical given its compact size and integration within the constrained space inside the wheel. However, the power loss caused by the switch contact resistance is minimal and, therefore, not considered in the overall motor loss.

Figure 4.1 presents the phase current profiles for the WLTP driving cycle of an Audi e-tron vehicle, featuring ELA's E-gear IWMs in each rear wheel. Figure 4.1 (a) illustrates the scenarios of fixed series or parallel configurations; while Figure 4.1 (b) provides a more practical profile based on the Case 1 e-gear shifting strategy outlined in Section 3.3.2. Additionally, thermal considerations of the E-gear system can be integrated into the development of high-level vehicle controls or E-gear shifting strategies to

proactively reduce thermal stress and enhance system reliability, particularly for situations where extreme high torque is demanded.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.1 IWM phase current profiles for the WLTP driving cycle.

4.2 Simulation of virtual motor temperature sensor

POLITO's virtual temperature sensor is based on lumped-parameter thermal network model or discrete state-space model, developed through detailed thermal simulations that account for an innovative motor cooling design. The virtual sensor estimates the motor's internal magnet and stator temperatures to ensure safe motor operation, which is particularly crucial when the motor utilises recycled magnets. This is due to the remanence of these magnets being highly sensitive to temperature variations. The model is validated against experimental data from ELA's baseline IWMs and will undergo further refinement for ELA's new IWM once it is prototyped and experimentally tested in a later stage of the project. Details of the virtual temperature sensor will be provided in document D4.3.

Figure 4.2 to Figure 4.4 present the simulation results of WLTP driving cycle of an Audi etron vehicle powered by two of ELA's baseline IWMs in the rear wheels at different ambient temperature. It is assumed that all brake scenarios are actuated via motor regenerative braking, as indicated by the negative torque in Figure 4.2 (a). The motor's responses in terms of power loss, rotor magnet temperature, and stator winding temperature are illustrated in Figure 4.2 (c), (d) and (e), respectively. Power loss acts as a heat source, influencing the temperatures, while temperature changes, in turn, affect the motor's electrical and magnetic properties, thereby impacting the power loss; this interplay is depicted by the red lines in the figure. During the WLTP driving cycle, the motor's magnet temperature rises by $\sim 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ from initial 40°C , while the winding temperature by $\sim 10^{\circ}\text{C}$ from initial 60°C . The magnet temperature shows a smoother variation, whereas the winding temperature fluctuates more due to the significant influence of torque demands on winding copper losses. For comparison, the temperature-independent power loss modelling is also presented as the blue lines. It can be observed that, under the given conditions of a coolant inlet temperature 60°C and an ambient temperature 20°C , the difference in power loss and temperature are negligible.

Figure 4.5 to Figure 4.7 show the simulation results for the Artemis motorway driving cycle at different ambient conditions. Compared to the WLTP driving cycle, the winding temperature shows a higher increase of $\sim 20^{\circ}\text{C}$, while the magnet temperature exhibits a variation. When considering the temperature independent power loss, the maximum difference in the winding temperature is $\sim 1.3^{\circ}\text{C}$, whereas the difference in the magnet temperature is negligible.

D 2.4 – Simulation results report

Figure 4.2 Motor responses of ELA's baseline IWM for WLTP driving cycle: Coolant 60°C, Ambient 20°C

Figure 4.3 Motor responses of ELA's baseline IWM for WLTP driving cycle: Coolant 70°C, Ambient 40°C

D 2.4 – Simulation results report

Figure 4.4 Motor responses of ELA's baseline IWM for WLTP driving cycle: Coolant 50°C, Ambient 10°C

Figure 4.5 Motor responses of ELA's baseline IWM for Artemis driving cycle: Coolant 70°C, Ambient 40°C

D 2.4 – Simulation results report

Figure 4.6 Motor responses of ELA's baseline IWM for Artemis driving cycle: Coolant 60°C, Ambient 20°C

Figure 4.7 Motor responses of ELA's baseline IWM for Artemis driving cycle: Coolant 50°C, Ambient 10°C

The temperature-dependent motor loss model is capable to reflect the impact of coolant and ambient temperatures. This level of detail is particularly important for a comprehensive motor thermal analysis, given the restricted space in in-wheel applications. Nevertheless, for the subsequent simulations presented in this document, the temperature-independent motor loss model will be employed but focus on the nominal 60°C coolant and 20°C ambient temperatures to minimise the inaccuracy.

4.3 Energy consumption assessment and improvement for IWM

To evaluate improvements in energy consumption across various vehicle segments, we analyse specific driving scenarios, such as constant-speed manoeuvres ranging from low to high speeds, as well as the WLTP driving cycle. These scenarios serve as a basis for comparing the performance of the E-gear IWM against the baseline IWM from ELA under varying conditions, providing a clear measure of its impact on overall energy efficiency. Additionally, the power consumption performance of the two rule-based gear-shifting strategies discussed in Section 3.3.2 is also analysed.

Table 4.1 provides a comparison of energy consumption per distance (Wh/km) between the new E-gear IWM and the baseline IWM across various vehicle segments and drivetrain configurations for different driving scenarios. The percentage improvement in energy efficiency is specifically evaluated for Case 1 rule-based gear shifting, relative to the baseline motor.

It is important to mention that regenerative braking is excluded from this analysis; hence, negative torques resulting from braking are not considered into the calculation of battery power consumption.

Table 4.1 Energy consumption per distance (Wh/km) and percentage difference in energy efficiency for various vehicle segments and drivetrains across different driving scenarios.

<i>WLTP driving cycle</i>				
Segment	Baseline ELA (Wh/km)	E-gear (Wh/km)		Energy/distance improvement (%)
		Rule-based case 1	Rule-based case 2	
A (2F-IWM)	160.3	138.5	138.3	13.6
B (2F-IWM)	164.8	150.3	150.2	8.8
C (2R-IWM)	169.3	154.8	154.6	8.56
D (2R-IWM)	158.66	130.47	129.96	17.76
Small Van (2F-IWM)	222.17	184.82	184.16	17.1
M (2R-IWM)	262.9	237.73	237.17	9.57
M (4-IWM)	273.75	245.45	245.27	10.34
<i>30 km/h constant speed manoeuvre</i>				
	Baseline ELA (Wh/km)	Energy/distance (Wh/km)	Winding configuration	
A (2F-IWM)	74.21	47.77	series	35.62
B (2F-IWM)	73.66	57.51	series	21.92
C (2R-IWM)	77.99	61.79	series	20.77
D (2R-IWM)	72.68	52.87	series	27.25

D 2.4 – Simulation results report

Small Van (2F-IWM)	97.83	77.6	series		20.67
M (2R-IWM)	115.93	97.92	series		15.53
M (4-IWM)	139.82	105	series		24.9
<i>50 km/h constant speed manoeuvre</i>					
A (2F-IWM)	95.57	70.48	series		26.25
B (2F-IWM)	92.33	75.82	series		17.88
C (2R-IWM)	95.06	78.51	series		17.41
D (2R-IWM)	83.88	63.54	series		24.25
Small Van (2F-IWM)	119.98	99.1	series		17.4
M (2R-IWM)	133	114.19	series		14.14
M (4-IWM)	158	121.66	series		23
<i>90 km/h constant speed manoeuvre</i>					
A (2F-IWM)	181.8	142.9	parallel		21.4
B (2F-IWM)	150.5	134.2	series		10.83
C (2R-IWM)	147.2	130.9	series		11.07
D (2R-IWM)	119.41	100.34	series		15.97
Small Van (2F-IWM)	193.67	173.94	series		10.18
M (2R-IWM)	189.51	171.17	series		9.67
M (4-IWM)	213.87	178.6	series		16.49
<i>120 km/h constant speed manoeuvre</i>					
A (2F-IWM)	276.8	219.6	parallel		20.66
B (2F-IWM)	222.2	199.5	parallel		10.22
C (2R-IWM)	211.6	189.3	parallel		10.54
D (2R-IWM)	168.81	148	parallel		12.3
Small Van (2F-IWM)	288.16	173.94	parallel		39.64
M (2R-IWM)	257.16	239.4	parallel		6.9
M (4-IWM)	280.9	248	parallel		11.7

As shown in Table 4.1 the use of the E-gear motor significantly reduces energy consumption compared to the baseline IWM. This highlights the effectiveness of the EM-TECH e-corner module solution in enhancing vehicle performance.

The variations in energy efficiency improvements across different vehicle segments are primarily influenced by factors such as vehicle mass, aerodynamics (drag coefficient and frontal area), and tyre rolling resistance. These characteristics affect the torque demand required to follow specific driving manoeuvres, such as constant-speed cruising and the WLTP driving cycle. Since the desired torque is determined by the speed controller to ensure the vehicle follows the target speed profile, different vehicle segments will require different torque inputs, leading to variations in energy consumption.

It is important to note that the power consumption values presented in the table are derived under ideal simulation conditions. Actual experimental values may be lower, making these figures approximate upper bounds.

Figure 4.8 depicts the speed tracking performance based on the WLTP driving cycle for the Segment M (2R-IWM) vehicle, using the rule-based Case 1 gear-shifting strategy.

Figure 4.8 Speed tracking performance for the WLTP driving cycle based on case 1 rule-based gear-shifting

We can see that the actual speed closely follows the driving cycle, demonstrating the vehicle's effective response and accurate speed tracking.

4.4 Brake blending strategy for energy recycling

The brake blending strategy analysed in this section is implemented on a separate simulation platform. The parameters of the vehicle model, including co-resistance force calculations, aerodynamics, and component losses, are scaled to align with the total energy consumption of the M-class model (2R-IWM) as determined for the baseline version using the VSM. Further parametrization to enhance model accuracy and applicability will be optimized in future work. To determine the effective range of the motor and how much energy is available for regeneration, the following map shows the amount of power the motor can output at a given speed and torque. This map also takes into account the energy losses in the stator and rotor of the motor.

Since the motor under study is equipped with the ability to switch windings from series to parallel, the map is shown in Figure 4.9 for both modes of operation.

Figure 4.9 Possible regeneration power for the motor, normalized to 100 units for the maximum power

From the normalized map in Figure 4.9 it can be seen that there is a range in which the motor is capable of producing up to 100 units of power, but at low speeds and high torques, such as in the series configuration, the motor is limited to about 30 units. There are areas where the motor is not capable of producing power and when the controller utilizes these areas, the regenerative torque will draw power from the battery.

In order to eliminate the areas that reduce the regenerative efficiency from the controller logic, a simple torque optimization function can be performed at different specified motor speeds, where the optimized parameter is the electrical power that is generated.

The result of such an efficiency map processing is shown in Figure 4.10. The left graph shows the maximum torque that the motor can efficiently handle for both series and parallel winding configurations. The right graph shows the maximum electrical power available during braking.

From the results, we can see that the parallel configuration achieves high values of regenerated energy, but there is a range where the series configuration works better. The series configuration allows much higher braking torques to be achieved, which can be useful when it is necessary to use a motor, for example, when using a motor for ABS or to reserve a friction braking system.

The calculated torque values are the upper limit for torque from the EM when the remainder of the torque requested by the driver is realized by the friction torque system.

Figure 4.10 Optimized regeneration torque and corresponding power available for braking

To validate the operation of the torque system controller, a series of tests were carried out based on a simulation model in Matlab/Simulink software, the vehicle model was parameterized according to the technical parameters of the Sport Utility Vehicle Audi e-tron equipped with two IWMs on the rear axle, using the efficiency maps of the base motor of the EM-Tech project.

The speed profile used for the WLTP test cycle was chosen as the cycle for evaluating the energy efficiency of the motor.

Simulations were performed for different models of brake blending controllers (parallel actuation of brake mechanism, series actuation of brake mechanism and considering the optimum torque) and their operation under different motor configurations, series winding or parallel winding. The main benchmark for evaluating the controller performance was the energy consumption in kW/100km.

Figure 4.11 Velocity tracking performance of brake blending controllers. Close speed values mean that all tested controllers were under equal test conditions.

Figure 4.12 Comparison of energy consumption of different configurations during a WLTP cycle

Figure 4.11 confirms that all controller models are able to pass the speed profile without significant deviations in speed tracking. Graph on Figure 4.12 shows the cumulative energy consumption during a cycle.

Figure 4.13 Simulated torque demanded from IWM during braking

Graphs on Figure 4.13 show the moment of the last deceleration on the drive cycle. The vehicle is braking from a high speed and the slow-down takes place over a long period of time. It is clearly visible how the requested torque values of the controller differ. For example, if we compare the first and last sub graphs, we can see that in the beginning the regeneration torque is higher, which leads to the fact that the optimal strategy allows to generate more energy, whereas by the moment of full stop the torque from the motor in the first graph becomes higher than the optimal one. When comparing the first and second sub-graphs, we can see that the torque is 2 times higher, and the difference in motor performance in parallel winding mode becomes apparent. This can be seen at the time of about 1780s.

This example clearly demonstrates the difference in the operation of the considered algorithms.

To evaluate the effect of the controller on driving efficiency, Table 4.2 shows the calculated energy consumption for the whole driving cycle.

Another interesting result of the controller test can be observed when the WLTP is split into ranges by speed.

- Low velocity region *Start of the cycle - 588s*
- Medium velocity region *588s - 1000s*

- High velocity region 1000s - 1474s
- Extra high velocity region 1474s - 1800s

Table 4.2 Results of controller testing on the WLTP cycle, divided by sections with different averages of velocities

Controller configuration	Low velocity region [kW/100km]	Medium velocity region [kW/100km]	High velocity region [kW/100km]	Extra high velocity region [kW/100km]	Combined [kW/100km]
No Brake Blending	18.56	22.79	33.35	34.39	26.53
Parallel phasing; series IWM	13.90	11.49	22.29	13.30	23.94
Parallel phasing; parallel IWM	14.10	10.26	23.01	13.88	24.22
Series phasing; series IWM	14.32	16.44	26.54	17.62	23.92
Series phasing; parallel IWM	14.22	13.14	22.27	13.29	24.19
Optimum; series IWM	13.83	10.19	20.10	13.20	23.90
Optimum; parallel IWM	14.18	12.59	23.09	13.11	24.19

According to the values in Table 4.2, it is possible to confirm that controllers that use optimization allow the lowest power consumption. At high speeds, a motor with a parallel configuration allows for more energy efficient driving. This occurs not only because of the higher ability to regenerate energy, but also because the motor consumes less energy at these loads.

The results obtained allow to evaluate the effect of integrating the controller into the vehicle, as well as to choose the most optimal configuration for the vehicle's powertrain.

4.5 Vehicle dynamics improvements for IWM applications using ABS

In this section, the simulation results for brake blending control in E-gear IWMs and the purely HB with low actuation frequency utilizing NMPC within an ABS framework, are presented. The IWMs from ELA function as additional actuators for the brake system, eliminating the drivetrain torsional dynamics and mechanical play. By directly manipulating the driver's reference torque, the IWMs complement the HB and enhance the torque response through superior wheel torque responsiveness, bandwidth and accurate torque actuation. The capability of IWMs utilizing in the NMPC with an ABS framework is investigated and the performance of the proposed ABS controller is assessed using several key performance indicators (KPIs) and compared with that of the ABS controller using only HB. The brake manoeuvre begins with the vehicle accelerating to 70 Km/h, followed by a sudden braking input until the

vehicle comes to a complete stop. This test scenario is conducted on a low-friction road with a constant low friction coefficient ($\mu = 0.5$).

4.5.1 Simulation results for hard braking manoeuvre with IWM

With the E-gear IWM configuration, the switch windings of IWMs can be connected in either series or parallel, extending the operational range in terms of torque and speed. During braking, the IWMs collaborate with the HB system to modulate brake torque and prevent wheel lock-up. The introduction of the IWMs provides the advantage of rapid torque response; however, the application of retarding torque is limited by factors such as the operational range, battery state of charge, motor speed, and operating temperature. Additionally, the EM must not remain active continuously when the vehicle comes to a complete stop. In a series configuration, the IWMs deliver maximum regenerative torque but operate at a lower speed limit, while a parallel configuration provides a higher speed range but with reduced regenerative torque. The gear-shifting strategy introduces a certain time delay in the motor's torque demand, leading to a temporary zero-torque demand. As shown in Figure 4.14, the reference brake torque at the front left (FL) wheel of the EM, $T_{ref_EM_FL}$, reach 800 Nm at 40 seconds. The NMPC controls the brake torque request of the EM, $T_{N_EM_FL}$, to follow the maximum brake torque. However, the actual brake torque from the EM, $T_{P_EM_FL}$, shows zero torque demands between 40.5 seconds and 40.8 seconds, lasting approximately 30 milliseconds, followed by a sudden increase to the maximum brake torque. During braking, this zero torque demand and abrupt jump in brake torque result in a rapid transition of torque demand from the motor to the HB system. This transition leads to fast oscillations in the manipulated torque of HB, which can degrade reference slip tracking performance and potentially cause damage to the HB system. To address this, a single gear is maintained during the brake manoeuvre.

Figure 4.14 Brake manoeuvre results with E-gear switching, regulated torque from the (a) IWM (b) HB

To evaluate the performance of the developed NMPC for ABS system, the following KPIs are defined based on the standard objective metrics for brake performance: d_{ABS} , the braking distance from ABS activation to when the vehicle speed reaches zero; $RMSE_{\sigma}$, the root means square error (RMSE) of the difference

between reference slip ratio, σ_{ref_FL} and the actual slip ratio, σ_{FL} ; σ_{max} , the maximum absolute value of slip ratio during braking; $IACA$, the integral of the absolute value of the control action; IP_{ABS} , The performance index comparing the brake distance with and without ABS control.

The simulation results below evaluate the ABS performance utilizing the proposed NMPC with brake blending and purely HB under the aforementioned KPIs. Simulations were conducted at an initial speed of 70 km/h with an overall torque demand of 10,000 Nm, where the cost function weighting matrices of the NMPC were optimized for both purely HB and braking blending configuration. The simulation results without ABS control are defined as passive configuration and evaluated using the same KPIs. As indicated in Table 4.3, all configurations demonstrated improvements in KPIs such as d_{ABS} , $RMSE_{\sigma}$, and IP_{ABS} . However, the purely HB configuration exhibited marginally reduced performance in d_{ABS} , σ_{max} , and $RMSE_{\sigma}$ compared to braking blending. Specifically, $RMSE_{\sigma a}$ represents the RMSE above the reference slip, σ_{ref} , while $RMSE_{\sigma b}$ represents the RMSE below σ_{ref} . The brake blending with EM configuration outperformed purely HB in terms of under-brake slip ratio, attributed to the faster actuator response time of the IWMs compared to the HB. The rapid torque response of the IWMs in the brake blending setup further enhanced braking. For the IWMs solution, series configuration provided higher regenerative torque than parallel configuration, leading to the performance in IP_{ABS} , d_{ABS} , σ_{max} and $RMSE_{\sigma}$. As the regenerative brake torque increased from parallel configuration to series configuration, the $IACA$ also increased due to higher manipulated torque from the IWMs. These results confirm that incorporating an IWMs improves braking performance by reducing braking distance, enhancing the reference slip tracking and vehicle stability, particularly during hard braking manoeuvres, thus showcasing the effectiveness the proposed controller.

Table 4.3 KPI values for the NMPC controllers for in-wheel configurations.

		In wheel						
Segment	Configuration	d_{ABS}	$RMSE_{\sigma}$	$RMSE_{\sigma a}$	$RMSE_{\sigma b}$	$IACA$	IP_{ABS}	σ_{max}
		[m]	[-]	[-]	[-]	[-]	[%]	[-]
Audi- etron	Passive	40.17	0.9119	0.0321	0.9930	31482	0	-1
	brake blending with E-gear IWMs (series configuration)	37.98	0.2813	0.0549	0.8500	EM: 11270.8	5.45	-0.0814
						HB: 3422.4		
	brake blending with E-gear IWMs (parallel configuration)	38.07	0.2870	0.0548	0.8904	EM: 6152.9	5.27	-0.0718
HB: 8530.9								
	Purely hydraulic brake	38.42	0.2875	0.0524	0.8773	14604.5	4.36	-0.0915

Figure 4.15 Brake manoeuvre results for purely hydraulic braking (a) wheel slip ratio (b) vehicle speed and wheel speed (c) regulate and unregulated torque from HB

Under constant low-friction road friction scenario ($\mu = 0.5$), NMPC ABS test results for different brake system configurations are detailed. To ensure sufficient brake torque during load transitions in hard braking scenarios, the brake allocation was at 0.8 for the front axle and 0.2 for the rear axles. For each tire, the vertical load was chosen such that the longitudinal force characteristic corresponds to the maximum achievable vehicle deceleration on the specified road surface. Across both tire-road friction levels, the selected reference slip ratio closely aligned with the peak longitudinal force. The time constant of the actuation time of HB is selected as in [3]. Figure 4.15 shows the performance of the purely hydraulic actuator, while Figure 4.16 and Figure 4.17 present brake blending results for series and parallel configurations, respectively. σ_{FL} is the actual slip ratio for the front left (FL) wheel; $\sigma_{passive_FL}$ is the passive slip ratio of the FL wheel; σ_{ref_FL} reference slip derived from the longitudinal tire force characteristics, calculated using the Pacejka MF. $T_{ref_HB_FL}$ is the reference torque of the HB in the FL wheel. $T_{N_HB_FL}$ and $T_{P_HB_FL}$ represent the actuation torque of the HB from the NMPC and the actuation torque of the HB applied to the vehicle, respectively.

D 2.4 – Simulation results report

As shown in Figure 4.15(a,b), during the brake manoeuvre, the passive brake system caused significant wheel locking under hard braking, leading to a sudden drop in the reference slip ratio. By contrast, the NMPC with purely HB prevented wheel locking until the ABS deactivated at vehicle speeds V_x and the rear left (RL) wheel speed below 7 km/h. The FL wheel speed $V_{\text{wheel_FL}}$ and RL wheel speed $V_{\text{wheel_RL}}$ tracked the vehicle speed, avoiding wheel locking. The HB torque regulation profiles in Figure 4.15(c) reveal that the average regulated torque was maintained at approximately 1800 Nm, increasing to the maximum value as the ABS is deactivated.

Based on the proposed NMPC controller, the nonlinear prediction model considering the dynamics of the E-gear IWMs is integrated to evaluate the ABS performance with brake blending. In Figure 4.16 (a) and Figure 4.17(a), it can be seen that the σ_{FL} is well-controlled with the implementation of EM, oscillating around the reference value after the initial peak. This performance, particularly under the specified low friction μ conditions, highlights the robustness of the NMPC controller with brake blending.

Figure 4.16 Brake manoeuvre results for brake blending in series configuration (a) wheel slip ratio (b) vehicle speed and wheel speed (c) regulated and unregulated torque from (c) HB (d) IWMs

D 2.4 – Simulation results report

When the IWMs winding was shifted, the motor torque request of FL wheel $T_{ref_EM_FL}$ increases from 800 Nm to 1500 Nm, reflecting the speed and torque characteristics of the IWMs. The high-level controller generated T_{ref_EM} based on wheel speed, resulting in a reduction in the reference torque between 20s to 20.7s as the vehicle decelerated. $T_{N_EM_FL}$ and $T_{P_EM_FL}$ represent the actuation torque of the EM from the NMPC and the actuation torque of the EM applied to the vehicle plant, respectively.

Due to the higher wheel torque response and bandwidth of the EM-TECH IWMs, the manipulated torque reacted almost instantaneously compared to the HB and closely followed the maximum reference torque, maximizing regenerative energy recovery. As the reference torque of the IWMs increased between 20 and 20.7 seconds, the HB compensated by decreasing its applied torque to meet the overall driver-requested reference torque.

The change in reference torque at the onset of braking resulted in an increase in the initial slip ratio, leading to a higher maximum slip ratio for series configurations compared to parallel configuration. However, series configuration's consistently higher regenerative braking torque throughout the braking operation enabled its slip trajectory to outperform parallel configuration's overall.

Figure 4.17 Brake manoeuvre results for brake blending in parallel configuration (a) wheel slip ratio (b) vehicle speed and wheel speed (c) regulated and unregulated torque from (c) HB (d) IWMs

5 Simulation results for onboard motors

5.1 Simulation of modular AFMs for a wide range of vehicle applications

The modular design of VAI’s AFMs allows for easy adaptation across various vehicle segments by adjusting the number of modules. For example, based on the representative vehicles outlined in EM-TECH D2.1, a single-module AFM is suitable for the Fiat 500e and Peugeot e-208, a two-module AFM for the VW ID.3, and a configuration of one single-module AFM for the front e-axle and one two-module AFM for the rear e-axle for the Audi e-tron. The transmission systems in this analysis are not specifically optimised but are modelled with a constant ratio based on the maximum motor speed and the vehicle's top speed.

The PWM frequency significantly affects the power losses in both the motor and the inverter. Generally, as the PWM frequency increases, inverter losses rise, while in the motor its copper losses tend to decrease, and rotor losses increase. However, thanks to the ironless design of VAI’s AFMs, the overall motor losses will decrease with higher PWM frequencies. As a result, an optimal PWM frequency can be identified to minimise the combined losses of the motor and inverter.

Table 5.1 Table 5.2 summarises the WLTP driving cycle simulation results for motor and inverter losses in vehicles equipped with modular e-axle solutions. A range of PWM frequencies from 32 kHz to 96 kHz was evaluated. The lowest selected frequency 32 kHz is sufficiently high to avoid significant harmonic issues. The results clearly show that as PWM frequency increases, motor losses decrease while inverter losses increase. Notably, a PWM frequency of 48 kHz yields the lowest combined motor and inverter losses. The motor variant showcased in the table represents a specific configuration of Vaionic’s platform, which can be readily adapted and optimized to meet diverse eDrive requirements by balancing performance, efficiency, and system cost, with design choices such as higher inverter currents enhancing motor efficiency but potentially increasing inverter costs, tailored ultimately to customer-specific needs.

Table 5.1 WLTP energy loss analysis under different PWM frequencies

PWM frequency [kHz]		32	48	64	80	96
Fiat 500e	Motor energy loss [Wh]	270	255	248	245	243
	Inverter energy loss [Wh]	23	35	46	58	69
	Combined energy loss [Wh]	293	290	294	303	312
Peugeot e-208	Motor energy loss [Wh]	256	242	235	231	229
	Inverter energy loss [Wh]	29	42	57	71	86
	Combined energy loss [Wh]	285	284	292	303	315
VW ID.3	Motor energy loss [Wh]	318	289	275	269	264
	Inverter energy loss [Wh]	35	53	70	88	106
	Combined energy loss [Wh]	353	342	345	357	370
Audi-e-tron	Motor energy loss - Front [Wh]	147	133	126	122	120
	Inverter energy loss - Front [Wh]	16	24	32	40	48

	Combined energy loss - Front [Wh]	163	157	157	162	168
	Motor energy loss - Rear [Wh]	258	229	215	209	205
	Inverter energy loss - Rear [Wh]	32	48	64	80	95
	Combined energy loss - Rear [Wh]	290	277	279	288	300

5.2 Energy consumption assessment and improvement for onboard motor

In this section, various driving cycles, such as WLTP, ECE-15 and J1015 as well as constant-speed manoeuvres, are used to assess the energy efficiency improvements achieved with the PnG controller.

The analysis uses the Volkswagen ID.3, a fully electric C-segment family car, along with the on-board motor data provided by TRX, which is specifically tuned for this C-segment vehicle. This evaluation considers different drivetrain configurations, including all-wheel-drive with two onboard motors (layout B) and rear-wheel-drive with a single motor on the rear axle (layout A). It is important to note that only positive motor torques are considered for the energy-per-distance performance analysis. Therefore, the braking torques are excluded from this analysis.

Table 5.2 presents the energy-per-distance improvement in terms of percentage for a Volkswagen ID.3 under two drivetrain configurations and various driving scenarios, both with and without the application of PnG. The comparison highlights how drivetrain choices and driving scenarios influence the vehicle's energy consumption across different conditions.

Table 5.2 Energy/distance improvement (%) for a Volkswagen ID.3 across different drivetrain configurations and driving scenarios, with and without the use of PnG strategies. Cruise mode is the reference (Ref) here.

Energy/distance improvement (%)							
Layout A				Layout B			
Cruise	LUT (level 1)	LUT (level 2)	LUT (level 3)	Cruise	LUT (level 1)	LUT (level 2)	LUT (level 3)
WLTP driving cycle							
Ref.	1.01	1.89	2.57	Ref.	8.45	10.31	11.96
ECE15 Driving cycle							
Ref.	1.74	2.94	3.49	Ref.	1.67	3.83	5.25
J1015 driving cycle							
Ref.	3.16	3.97	4.48	Ref.	3.9	6.39	7.45
50 km/h constant speed manoeuvre							
Ref.	2.78	5.65	7.54	Ref.	2.34	7.69	11.18
90 km/h constant speed manoeuvre							
Ref.	3.5	5.83	7.4	Ref.	4.9	9.6	12.6
120 km/h constant speed manoeuvre							
Ref.	2.56	4.47	5.84	Ref.	6.51	10.46	13.05

Table 5.2 demonstrates improved energy-per-distance performance in the LUT Level 3 case, where a more reduction of power loss near zero torque is observed compared to other two levels. Overall, PnG consistently enhances energy efficiency, with greater benefits observed in Mode B.

Furthermore, there is a greater reduction in power usage at constant speeds, as the consistent application of PnG contributes to improved performance.

Figure 5.1 illustrates the speed tracking performance for a 50 km/h constant speed manoeuvre, comparing scenarios with and without the use of PnG.

Figure 5.1 Speed tracking performance for a 50 km/h constant speed manoeuvre, comparing results with (b) and without (a) the application of Pulse-and-Glide (PnG).

The impact of the PnG strategy is clearly evident in Figure 5.1 (b), where a periodic pattern occurs every 2 seconds (PnG period), alternating between pulsing and gliding phases. Despite using pulse and glide, the vehicle maintains a constant speed of 50 km/h, demonstrating efficient power consumption without sacrificing speed consistency.

From a comfort viewpoint, studies in the literature have identified limits in terms acceptable longitudinal jerk, measured with real human users. For a practical implementation of PnG a trade-off must be found in terms of implementation frequency, in order to respect the identified comfort limits, whilst guaranteeing a reduction in energy consumption.

5.3 Vehicle dynamics improvements for onboard applications using ABS

This section presents the simulation results of brake blending with an onboard AFM from TRX, integrated into an ABS framework employing NMPC, compared to a purely HB system. The evaluation is conducted on an Audi e-tron vehicle equipped with a single onboard motor at the front axle. While the onboard configuration offers the advantage of reducing unsprung mass, it simultaneously introduces torsional dynamics from the drivetrain, resulting in nonlinear phenomena such as torsional oscillation in the drive shaft and backlash in the gearbox system. The high-power-density AFM motor, integrated with the gearbox, enhances the ABS by providing high brake torque manipulation. The NMPC framework

D 2.4 – Simulation results report

incorporates the gear ratio of the drivetrain and predicts its behaviour in advance to enhance braking performance. The block diagram shown in Figure 5.2 represents the block diagram implemented in VSM, including backlash and torsional behaviour of the driving shaft. Based on the corresponding wheel radius of the vehicle and the maximum speed of 1500 rpm for the in-wheel motor configuration, the conversion to the onboard solution with the TRX motor is performed by defining a gear ratio of 6.5.

Figure 5.2 Torsional dynamics of the onboard solution

The simulation model with torsional dynamics captures the effects of rotational inertia and stiffness in the half shaft and gearbox. In contrast, a system without torsional dynamics assumes rigid connections, simplifying the model but potentially neglecting critical dynamic phenomena. The torque response from the motor, as well as the torque after the gearbox and half shaft to the wheel, is depicted in Figure 5.3.

The vehicle manoeuvre aligns with those described in Section 4.5. The implementation of the gearbox amplifies the motor's reference torque from 379 Nm to 1232 Nm. Additionally, the inclusion of torsional dynamics introduces realistic transient responses, such as torque oscillations during acceleration and deceleration, particularly during large torque transitions. These dynamics characteristics provide a more realistic consideration for the surrogate model of regenerative braking, especially when the motor manipulates the brake torque.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.3 Torque response of the motor (a) with (b) without torsional dynamics

5.3.1 Simulation results for hard braking manoeuvre with onboard AFM

This section presents the simulation results evaluating the control performance of the proposed NMPC, assessed under the same KPIs and braking scenario described in Section 4.5. As shown in

Table 5.3, both HB and brake blending demonstrate improvements in KPIs. While brake blending exhibits better performance compared to HB, these simulation results align with the conclusions drawn in Section 4.5.

Table 5.3 KPI values for the NMPC controllers for on-board configurations.

Segment	Configuration	On-board						
		d_{ABS} [m]	$RMSE_{\sigma}$ [-]	$RMSE_{\sigma a}$ [-]	$RMSE_{\sigma b}$ [-]	$IACA$ [-]	IP_{ABS} [%]	σ_{max} [-]
Audi e-tron	Passive	40.17	0.9119	0.0321	0.9930	31482	0	-1
	Brake blending with on-board AFM	37.85	0.2849	0.0420	0.9739	EM: 9473.50	5.77	-0.0671
						HB: 6094.15		
Purely hydraulic	38.47	0.2865	0.0517	0.9333	14652.9	4.36	-0.0797	

D 2.4 – Simulation results report

Figure 5.4 Brake manoeuvre results for purely hydraulic braking (a) wheel slip ratio (b) vehicle speed and wheel speed (c) regulate and unregulated torque from HB

As shown in Figure 5.4 and Figure 5.5, both HB and brake blending demonstrate robust control in preventing wheel locking. However, brake blending outperforms HB in terms of in KPIs due to the motor's fast response time and the amplified reference braking torque provided by the gearbox system. Compared to the in-wheel motor configuration, the onboard configuration exhibits greater oscillatory effects at the start of braking manoeuvre, likely caused by the torsional dynamics of the drive shaft inducing oscillatory braking torque on the wheel. Nonetheless, the findings consistently indicate that brake blending enhances braking performance under constant friction conditions, aligning with the observations in Section 4.5.

D 2.4 – Simulation results report

Figure 5.5 Brake manoeuvre results for brake blending (a) wheel slip ratio (b) vehicle speed and wheel speed (c) regulate and unregulated torque from (c) HB (d) on-board motor

6 Use of the in-wheel and onboard motor solutions for AI-based traction control applications

Traction controllers are a class of longitudinal slip controllers that adjust the driver’s traction torque request to limit wheel slip, and in doing so, maximize tire force generation and maintain vehicle stability [4]. The functionality of TC is particularly beneficial on low tire-road friction conditions, where relatively small torque requests can induce very fast wheel dynamics (beyond the driver's control), yielding significant wheel slips and, possibly, spinning of the vehicle. This section targets to assess at vehicle level ELA and TRA motors for TC applications. To this aim the AI-based TC algorithm discussed in D5.2 has been implemented and integrated within the simulation toolchain described in D2.3 and tested for 2 vehicle segments for in-wheel and onboard solutions. The artificial intelligence (AI) controller is based on a deep reinforcement learning (DRL) strategy. In this framework the controller or agent is a neural network (NN) which maps a set of states, also known as observations, on the control action. Specifically, in the DRL framework the agent selects the control input (also denoted as action) based on a set of observations from the environment, consisting of the system to control along with its relevant disturbances. The policy that links observations to actions is learnt by the agent through its interaction with the environment, aiming to maximize a cumulative reward over multiple simulated sequences, known as episodes. In the case of the TC controller used with the ELA baseline motor and TRA EM, the control action used to steer the slip dynamics to a reference one is the torque correction T_{corr} to the total vehicle torque demand, while the observations include information such as the wheel slip, vehicle acceleration, motor torque demand and actual torque, and previous torque correction. Finally the reward function includes terms promoting a good closed-loop tracking performance of the reference slip and terms based on the control action to limit its rate of variation and magnitude, i.e., for avoiding saturation of the control action. Figure 6.1 shows the learning scheme underlining the DRL-TC method composed by the agent implemented in Simulink and the environment implemented in AVL VSM and Simulink. Further details about the DRL controller are reported in D5.2.

Figure 6.1 Simplified schematic of the training framework of the DRL-TC

The proposed DRL agent is trained on two electric vehicles (EVs) , i.e., a front wheel drive (FWD) city car (from EU vehicle segment A) and a rear wheel drive (RWD) (from EU vehicle segment D), with two different powertrain architecture each (in wheel and on board) generating four DRL-based TCs. The training scenario of the proposed DRL-TC agent is a straight-line acceleration from standstill with a sudden change of the friction coefficient. The scenario starts on high-friction asphalt, i.e., road-tire friction level $\mu = 1$. After 1 s the EV vehicle crosses low- μ patch ($\mu = 0.3$) covering the whole lane. The test starts with low torque demand, which is then increased at 0.5 s to a reference value that generates wheel spinning. Figure 6.2 provide an example of the training plot of the proposed DRL-TC agent for the segment A vehicle, on-

board configuration. The black solid line represents the episodic reward while the red one is the average reward over the last 10 episodes. The training is considered completed at 1000 episodes because the reward increases until around round 400 and then remains mostly constant, meaning the agent has found a stable solution.

Figure 6.2 DRL training, segment A: episodic reward (black solid line) and average reward (red solid line)

The wheel slip S_x is expressed as a percentage. Figure 6.3 shows the simulation results, wheel slip and torque demand, in the case of in-wheel motors and compare them to the those obtained with the corresponding passive vehicle, i.e., without TC active. The simulation results for the onboard configuration are instead reported in Figure 6.4.

Figure 6.3 Simulation results, wheel slip and torque request in the case of in-wheel powertrains: (a) Segment A and (b) Segment D.

Figure 6.4 Simulation results, wheel slip and torque request in the case of onboard motor powertrain: (a) Segment A and (b) Segment D.

As shown in Figure 6.3 and Figure 6.4, during the tire-road friction jump, in the case of the passive vehicles a significant wheel spinning occurs when the front axle enters the low-friction area, with a drop in longitudinal vehicle acceleration (see Figure 6.5). On the other hand, when the TCs are active, the motor torque request T_{req} is reduced to meet the slip ratio constraint and increase longitudinal acceleration. More in detail, for the Segment A FWD vehicle, a maximum slip ratio of $\sim 25\%$, converging to the reference in less than a second (see Figure 6.4 (a) and Figure 6.5 (a)). Consequently, an average improvement of $\sim 10\%$ in maximum longitudinal acceleration in low friction conditions (see also Figure 6.5). Similar results are obtained for the RWD segment D vehicle.

Figure 6.5 Vehicle acceleration for segment A (a) onboard and (b) in-wheel solution.

7 Conclusion

In conclusion, the simulation toolchain developed in WP2 has proven to be a pivotal asset in advancing the EM-TECH project by facilitating the integration, evaluation, and iterative improvement of innovative e-axle and e-corner technologies. This toolchain examines the impact of design decisions on vehicle-level performance, offering detailed insights into energy efficiency, thermal behaviour, and advanced control strategies such as pulse-and-glide, ABS, TC, gear-shifting, and virtual sensing techniques across WLTP and real-world operation scenarios.

By consolidating data and enabling comprehensive system simulations, the toolchain bridges the gap between component-level development and vehicle-level performance assessment, ensuring alignment with technical requirements and design objectives. The adaptability of the toolchain supports rapid updates and re-parameterization, allowing seamless incorporation of advancements from component suppliers and fostering robust collaboration among project partners.

Moreover, the simulation results have provided actionable insights that guide early-stage experimental XIL and HIL system development. This capability not only accelerates the R&D process but also equips the project to address diverse operational conditions and meet the specific needs of prospective OEMs. The toolchain's capacity to simulate real-world scenarios as a comprehensive framework for evaluating and optimizing next-generation electric machine technologies, enabling improved performance, efficiency, and reliability. Ultimately, the simulation environment offers a scalable and efficient approach to enhancing vehicle performance, improving energy efficiency, and driving sustainable innovations for the potential Tier 1 suppliers or OEM vehicle targets.

In the course of the deliverable preparation, an amendment to the grant agreement has been performed to replace VAI by TRX. Consequently, both technologies have been incorporated into the simulation analysis for vehicles with onboard motors, and the results are presented in this deliverable.

7.1 Deviations, Impact and Recovery Actions

This deliverable is delayed by six weeks to perform the review for public release.

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